

Terraforming Jupiter

Period of Time: 27th-30th century

Surface area compared to Earth: 120 times

Maximum population hosted after terraforming: \approx 900B+ people

Company involved in the process of creating habitats: **NAR** (Ndoni Advanced Robotics)

Number of robots involved in the construction: 350B+

Purpose: after terraforming Jupiter, build a habitat and infrastructure for (potentially) hosting more than 900B people to live on the planet using robots and advanced machinery.

© *Copyright*

Albi Ndoni
Tirana, Albania
05/17/2023